

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF ARGININE IN THE TREATMENT OF GENERALIZED FORMS OF PERIODONTITIS

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Abstract

Periodontal disease is the most common human disease. The problem of rational treatment of generalized periodontitis is relevant. In the complex treatment of generalized periodontitis, various groups of medications are traditionally used. Today, the role of nitric oxide in the development of various pathological processes attracts attention. Important links in the development of generalized periodontitis are oxidative stress, disturbances in nitric oxide metabolism and hemomicrocirculation. All this necessitates correction of these mechanisms of the pathogenesis of generalized periodontitis in its complex treatment. For this purpose, arginine preparations can be used, since L-arginine is a source of nitric oxide formation.

Keywords: arginines, generalized periodontitis.

Purpose: to study the clinical effectiveness of the use of the proposed pharmacological composition with arginine in the complex treatment of generalized periodontitis.

Materials and methods. A comprehensive examination of the condition of the periodontal tissues of patients before and after treatment was carried out. To assess the clinical effectiveness of treatment, the Shiler-Pisarev test (1962), the PMA index according to C. Parma (1961), the Fedorov-Volodkina hygienic index (1978) and the vacuum test according to Kulazhenko (1961) were used. The results of the study were established. The inclusion of the proposed pharmacological composition in the complex therapy of patients with generalized periodontitis makes it possible to more effectively suppress the dystrophic-inflammatory process in periodontal tissues. This confirms a decrease in the PMA index, an increase in the time of hematoma formation during the Kulazhenko vacuum test, and an improvement in the level of oral hygiene.

Periodontal disease is the most common disease. Affected periodontal tissues have an adverse effect on the body and can cause the occurrence of a chronoseptic condition. Taking this into account, the problem of rational treatment of periodontal diseases, and especially generalized periodontitis, is relevant [5, 7, 13, 15]. antiseptics, antibiotics, antifungal and antiprotozoal drugs), proteolytic enzymes and proteolysis inhibitors, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, immunomodulators, calcium preparations, antiresorbents, etc. An important place is occupied by drugs that affect metabolic processes in periodontal tissues and have a membrane-stabilizing and, thus, periodontal protective effect. Today, the role of nitric oxide in the develop-

ment of various pathological processes attracts attention [1–4]. It takes part in fundamental biological processes: blood circulation and normalization of blood pressure, activity of the central and autonomic nervous system, metabolic processes, activation of the immune system, etc. It has been shown that one of the important intimate potentials for the development of periodontal diseases are manifestations of NO-dependent endothelial dysfunction [17]. Against the background of activation of free radical oxidation processes and depletion of the protective antioxidant system, significant morpho-functional changes were found in the structure of the ash microvascular endothelium with inhibition of the activity of endothelial NO synthase [6, 18]. Thus, it has been shown that important links in the development of generalized periodontitis are oxidative stress, impaired nitric oxide metabolism and hemomicrocirculation. All this necessitates correction of these mechanisms of the pathogenesis of generalized periodontitis in its complex treatment. For this purpose, arginine preparations can be used, since L-arginine is a source of nitric oxide formation. The purpose of this work was to determine the clinical effectiveness of the proposed pharmacological composition with arginine in the complex treatment of generalized periodontitis. treatment of 25 patients with chronic generalized periodontitis (grades I and II). The average age of the patients was 38 ± 3 years. The average number of men was 10, women – 15. In the treatment of generalized periodontitis of patients in this group, the proposed pharmacological composition was used. The control group was a group of ten patients of the same age with a similar degree and nature of the course of generalized periodontitis. Treatment of generalized periodontal disease was carried out according

to the traditional generally accepted method using mephenamine sodium salt. When making a diagnosis, we used the classification of periodontal diseases according to M.F. Danilevsky [8]. A comprehensive examination of the condition of the periodontal tissues of patients before and after treatment was carried out. Local removal of all factors irritating periodontal tissue and drug treatment was carried out using the proposed pharmacological composition and antibacterial drugs in accordance with the nature of the microflora.

Method of local treatment The proposed method of treatment was carried out as follows. After removing dental plaque and other periodontal tissue irritants, professional teeth cleaning was carried out using ultrasonic and ultrafine methods using the AirFlow system. After this, the proposed pharmacological composition in the form of a suspension was applied to the selected periodontal area for 10–20 minutes. Patients were asked to carry out such procedures at home. After brushing your teeth with Parodontax toothpaste, apply the pharmacological composition: squeeze out Cholisal gel (1 cm strip) into a tablespoon, add Cardioarginine syrup (10–15 drops) and peppermint essential oil (1–2 drops). The resulting suspension was thoroughly mixed and the application was applied to selected areas of the gum mucosa for 20 minutes, rubbing in for 2 minutes. After this, Parodontax rinse aid was used. The procedure was carried out twice a day, morning and evening. The course of treatment is 14 days. In the control group of patients, the treatment was similar, but instead of the proposed pharmacological composition, mephenamine sodium salt was used. To assess the clinical effectiveness of treatment, the Schiller-Pisarev test, the C. Parma PMAza index [24], the Fedorov-Volodkina hygienic index, and the Kulazhenko vacuum test [14] were used. Statistical processing of the study results was carried out using the Student criterion [16].

Results and discussion A comprehensive examination of patients with generalized periodontitis of I–II degrees showed the presence of a pronounced dystrophic inflammatory process in periodontal tissues. 3, the Shiller-Pisarev test was positive in all patients. The PMA index in patients with generalized periodontitis of I–II degrees averaged $62.2 \pm 0.58\%$. The stability of the gum vessels was reduced; a vacuum hematoma formed on average after 13.2 ± 1.1 s. After treatment with traditional methods, patients in the control group achieved a pronounced anti-inflammatory effect. The hygienic index according to Fedorov-Volodkin averaged 1.9 ± 0.3 , the Schiller-Pisarev test was weakly positive in 4 (40.0%) patients. $.5 \pm 0.5\%$. The resistance of the gum vessels was increased, a vacuum hematoma was formed on average after 19.5 ± 1.7 s. The hygienic index according to Fedorov-Volodkin averaged 1.3 ± 0.2 ; The Shiller-Pisarev test was weakly positive in one (5%) patient. The PMA index in patients with generalized periodontitis of I–II degrees averaged $24.5 \pm 0.55\%$. The stability of the gum vessels was significantly increased; a vacuum hematoma was formed on average after 28.5 ± 1.7 s. A decrease in the level of the inflammatory process in periodontal tissues after the use of the proposed pharmacological composition is also evidenced by an improvement in the level of oral hygiene in patients. It was

determined using the Fedorov-Volodkina hygienic index. Before treatment, the level of hygiene in patients was assessed as poor. In patients with generalized periodontitis I–II degrees, it was 3.2 ± 0.3 . The state of oral hygiene improved slightly after traditional treatment. In particular, the hygienic index in patients with generalized periodontitis of degrees I–II was 1.9 ± 0.3 . The level of oral hygiene increased more significantly in patients with generalized periodontitis, in whom the proposed pharmacological composition was used during treatment. In general, it was rated as satisfactory and amounted to 1.3 ± 0.2 . A decrease in the degree of activity of the dystrophic inflammatory process in periodontal tissues under the influence of the proposed pharmacological composition is also evidenced by an increase in the time of hematoma formation under the influence of a dosed vacuum (Kulazhenko test). When analyzing the results of the study, it was noted that a hematoma in the area of 31, 32, 41, 42 teeth in patients with I–II degrees of generalized periodontitis formed within 13.2 ± 1.1 s (before treatment), 19.5 ± 1.7 s (after treatment with traditional methods) and 28.5 ± 1.7 s when the proposed pharmacological composition was included in the complex treatment regimen. One of the indicators of the clinical effectiveness of the use of the proposed pharmacological composition in the complex treatment of patients with generalized periodontitis was also a decrease in the patients' subjective sensations during the treatment: pain, a feeling of heat, itching in the spring, a decrease in gum swelling. In patients in the control group, when using the traditional treatment regimen, subjective sensations decreased on the 5th day in 40.0% of patients, completely stopped on the 8th day in 60.0% of patients and on the 10th day in 70.0%. % of patients. When the proposed pharmacological composition was included in complex treatment, the sensation of pain, itching, heat in the gums and swelling of the gums significantly decreased on the 3rd day in 13 (65.0%) patients, and completely stopped on the 5th day in 17 (85.0%) patients, on the 8th day – in 19 (95.0%) patients. Thus, the inclusion of the proposed pharmacological composition in the complex therapy of patients with generalized periodontitis significantly reduces the time of its treatment. periodontal This is confirmed by a decrease in the PMA index, an increase in the time of hematoma formation during the Kulazhenko vacuum test, and an improvement in the level of oral hygiene.

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